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Reforming and Creating a Business-Friendly Environment: An Empirical Case Study of (*Non-Profit Organization*) in Nigeria

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Abstract

As a religious country, the people's faith has influenced business behavior and actions. Some residents view their religion as a culture, way of life, trust-currency, and/or a segregation index. Previous studies have analyzed and attributed corruption in Nigeria as the primary cause of the dwindling economy, attributing a direct and sometimes indirect correlation to the nation's focus on religion as the catalyst of the country's problem. This article is an internal whitepaper of the Ane Osiobe International Foundation's activities, utilizing its costs of operation and estimated budget for future projects to analyze the economic impact of corruption on the Nigerian economy's business-friendly environment, attraction, and retention. The impact results show the direct, indirect, and induced effects of a hostile business environment as non-profit organizations try to help residents of the Nigerian economy, and the government places a heavy tax burden on their donations under section 12-A of the Nigerian tax code and the indirect bureaucratic corrupted processes on every activity that can promote economic growth and development within the region; which is simply an indirect, self-induced economic war against the Nigerian people that in turn creates a vicious domino-and-multiplier effect against the nation in the international market. The recommendation from the study builds on the premise that the most valuable asset to combat this hostile virtuous cycle is trust and transparency not only at the national level but where it is most needed, which is the individual level.

Keywords: Business-Friendly Environment, Religion, Economic Impact, Bureaucratic Activities

1. Introduction

Nigeria is a very religious [Christianity, Islam, and Paganism (polytheism or ethnic-tradition)] country. The nation is known for its rich culture, afro-music, natural resource, and multilingual ethnicity, but this study will be focused on its business environment from a non-profit perspective and how hostile the business environment is to stakeholders. The Nigerian business environment can be summarized in one word both from the banking, natural resource, education, and non-profit sector; "corrupt." According to the Transparency International Index, corruption is the abuse of entrusted power and privileges for private gain. Nigeria ranks 154 out of 180 countries with a score of 24/100 based on 2021 (Corruption Perception Index (CPI), 2022). Eighty-five percent of the participants believe corruption in the country keeps increasing based on the study trends (Transparency International (TI), 2015). According to the Global Corruption Barometer (GCB), 43 percent thought corruption

increased in the previous 12 months, and 44 percent of public service users paid a bribe in the previous 12 months (GCB, 2019).

Figure 1: Corruption Perceptions Index

Source: (CPI, 2022)

Figure 1 shows the CPI of Nigeria; a low score out of 100 indicates that the country is highly corrupted, while a high score indicates that the country is transparent in its dealings. Researchers such as but are not limited to (Ajie and Wokekoro, 2012; Egger and Winner, 2005; Anokhin and Schulze, 2009); have indicated that corruption can be linked to the economy (natural resources, trade, and international agreements) and non-economic (religion, trust, and culture) factors which have had a net negative impact on the growth and development of the country. Hence, associating most emerging economies located in South America, Africa, and Asia with low CPIs, between 39 (Colombia, Ethiopia, Guyana, Kosovo, Morocco, North Macedonia, Suriname, Tanzania, and Vietnam) – 11 (South Sudan) with (Denmark, Finland, and New Zealand) ranking top of the list with 88/100 (CPI, 2022) in both the private and public sectors.

Figure 2: CPI 2022

Source: (CPI, 2022)

Figure 2 shows the CPI of the 180 countries on the continental map or the world with 100/light yellow meaning less corrupt or very clean and 0/dark red meaning highly corrupt for the year 2021. According to Transparency International, the global average of CPI remained the same for the last decade, at 43/100 points. Despite multiple commitments by sovereign governments, 131 nations have made zero significant progress against corruption in the last ten years (2011 – 2021). Two-thirds of countries on the world map and 100% of the countries in Africa score below 50, indicating severe corruption problems, while 27 countries are at their lowest score ever. Based on the Transparency International analysis (CPI, 2022), human rights are crucial in the fight against corruption: countries with well-protected civil liberties generally score higher on the CPI, while countries who violate civil liberties tend to score lower.

Figure 3: CPI 2022

Source: (CPI, 2022)

Figure 3 shows that Nigeria scores below the world's CPI average with a 24/100, tying with (The Central African Republic and Lebanon) which indicates that the country is highly corrupted with a declining trend see Figure 1.

Table 1: Top 25 worst Currencies in Africa

Ranking	Country (Name of Currency)	1 USD to
1	Sao Tome & Principe (Dobra)	20,901
2	Sierra Leonean (Leone)	10,105
3	Guinea-Bissau (West-African CFA Franc)	9,953
4	Guinea (Guinean Franc)	9,930
5	Equatorial Guinea (Central African CFA franc)	9,905
6	Malagasy (Ariary)	3,735
7	Uganda (Shilling)	3,671
8	Tanzania (Shilling)	2,319
9	Burundi (Franc)	1,944
10	Rwanda (Franc)	987
11	Malawi (Kwacha)	765
12	Nigeria (Naira)	625
13	Somali (Shilling)	585
14	Burkina Faso (West African CFA Franc)	541
14	Cote d'Ivoire (West African CFA Franc)	541
14	Togo (West African CFA Franc)	541
14	Benin Republic (West African CFA Franc)	541

14	Mali (West African CFA Franc)	541
14	Niger (West African CFA Franc)	541
14	Senegal (West African CFA Franc)	541
21	Gabon (Central African CFA Franc)	540
21	Cape Verde (Central African CFA Franc)	540
23	Cameroon's (West African CFA Francs)	539
24	Comoros (Comorian Franc)	407
25	Zimbabwe (Zimbabwean Dollar)	362

Source: (Baha, 2022)

Table 1 shows that the Nigerian Naira is the 12th weakest and list valuable currency in Africa, weaker than the Zimbabwean dollar. The monetary policy power of the Central Bank of Nigeria is so weak that the black market rate at the exchange market overpowers the CBN official rate. Today, the naira has little value among its pairs in Africa and is even weaker against other countries worldwide. According to the World Development Index (WDI), Nigeria is the biggest economy on the continent, ranked as the 26th-largest economy in the world in terms of nominal GDP, with 432.3 billion USD as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as of 2020 (WDI, 2022), most of its citizens live in poverty which has a high correlation to the level of the nation's corruption. Nevertheless, its leaders still borrow money from foreign nations like China and international organizations like the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF), putting pressure on its local currency in terms of the interest rate. This effect is not due to borrowing but use of the funds. The evidence will show that the money is not used for capital investments but for consumption only, which is plagued with a high corruption CPI. As an effect of the weakening economy and public fund mismanagement, the nation is faced with a high rate of brain drainage.

The contribution of this study to the literature on business attraction, retention, and a business-friendly environment is that the research investigates how the corruption level in Nigeria has affected the country's business environment and the negative economic impact (direct, indirect, and induced) effects of deadweights on the economy. Our analysis utilizes the Ane Osioke International Foundation's ((AOIF) Financial Records (AOIFFR)) as a case study for empirical analysis. The limitation of the study is that some of the analyses are based on projected expenditure numbers and not actual expenditure figures.

2. Previous Literature

Corruption is a social phenomenon that is hard to define empirically or theoretically because what is corruption or unethical in a community can be seen as a way of life and ethical in another. Hence, to define corruption, factors like but are not limited to history, politics, social-and-cultural norms, beliefs, the rule of law, and the economic status quo need to be factored into the definition. A theatrical-based study asserts that democracy [which universally is more favored as an economic system compared to dictatorship] has primarily led to the reduction of corruption and promoted economic growth and development (Treisman, 2000), which can be supported by the current standard of living in most democratic western countries. Westernized countries like the United States, Canada, Switzerland, and Israel that practice western democracy are known for their higher level of residents' participation. As a result, their higher level of public participation in the nation's governance leads to economic growth and development (Scully & Slottje, 1991; Vorhies & Glahe, 1988). According to (Alesina et al., 2003), ethnic conflict is one of the essential determinants of political economy. Many believe that the lack of an ethical system that favors all residents in a nation will lead to fractured institutions, political instability, and a decline in economic growth and development. Alesina et al. (2003) support (Easterly & Levine's, 1997) analysis that per capita GDP has an inverse relationship with ethnolinguistic fractionalization in African countries, arguing that much of their economic growth and development failure is due to ethical conflict.

3. Methodology

The author used the IMPLAN software to estimate the direct, indirect, and induced economic impact(s) of a hostile business environment. The result depicts the economic deadweight due to the Nigerian government's hostile

dealings with businesses. The appropriateness of this model for this study is justified as IMPLAN is the only Input-Output data company that has the aggregate labor force information on Nigeria (Osiobe, 2018).

3.1. Data

The study used publicly available data from the foundations' audited financial reports from 2015 to 2021 (AOIFFR, 2022).

Table 2: Data 1

Year	Expenditure Report ₦	Donations Reports ₦	Total Expenditure ₦	Change in Total Expenditure ₦
2015	791,350.00	-	791,350.00	-
2016	2,029,300.00	250,000.00	2,279,300.00	188.03%
2017	2,430,603.00	650,000.00	3,080,603.00	35.16%
2018	4,410,327.00	91,400.00	4,501,727.00	46.13%
2019	2,923,132.00	1,200,000.00	4,123,132.00	-8.41%
2020	1,150,027.00	9,000,000.00	10,150,027.00	146.17%
2021	15,000,000.00	-	15,000,000.00	47.78%
Total	28,734,739.00	11,191,400.00	39,926,139.00	-

Source: (AOIFFR, 2022)

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Table 3: Data 2

Project Name	Estimated cost ₦
Project – Nayomee	101,000,000.00
Project – Evergreen	50,000,000.00
Project – Woodbury	50,000,000.00
Transactional Cost	49,000,000.00
Total	250,000,000.00

Source: (AOIF Unpublished Statements, 2022)

3.2. Methodology

The study methodology builds on (Osiobe, 2018 & 2019) while expanding on the model.

$$Y_i = \beta_i X_1 + \dots + \beta_{i25} X_{25} + \varepsilon_i$$

The Input-Output model shows the relationships/multiplier effect of the monetary transaction from one industrial sector within an economy that may translate [become an input] to another industrial sector within the same economy—showing how dependent each sector is on the other, both as a demander of outputs and as a supplier of inputs.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{1,1} & \dots & \beta_{1,25} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \beta_{25,1} & \dots & \beta_{25,25} \end{pmatrix}, B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ \vdots \\ b_{25} \end{pmatrix}, C = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_{25} \end{pmatrix}$$

Where:

A = input-output matrix

B = externa; demand vector

C = production level vector

$$Y = AC + B$$

Where:

$$A \text{ and } B \neq \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The study also builds on the Leontief Model [Leontief Inverse Matrix or Total Requirement Matrix] (Leontief, 1966):

$$\begin{aligned} I_n Y - AC &= B \\ (I_n - A)Y &= B \\ Y &= (I_n - A)^{-1}B \end{aligned}$$

3.3. Model Information

Table 4: Model Information

Software Year	2011
Model Status	Multiplier
Multiplier Specification	SAM
Gross Regional Production	₦ 35,106,462,154,698
Total Personal Income	₦ 21,315,290,000,000
Number of Industries in the model	25
Land Area (Square Miles)	356,667
Population	206,100,000
Average Household Income	₦636,084

Source: (Implan 11 software and Database for Nigeria, 2022) & author's modification to current data (WDI,2022)

4. Findings

Figure 4: Expenditure Report

Source: (AOIFFR, 2022)

Figure four shows the expenditure report of AOIF from 2015 to 2021 as a percentage of the foundation's yearly spending. The pie chat shows 2021 at 52%, 2018 at 15%, 2019 at 10%, 2017 at 9%, 2016 at 7%, 2020 at 4%, and 2015 at 3%.

4.1. 2015 Expenditure and Donation Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2015 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 10, in the Appendix Section (AS)), shows that the total labor income was ₦ 87,491; the mean labor income was ₦ 29,163.33k; the median labor income was ₦ 3,940; the range of the labor income was ₦ 77,634 (with a min of ₦ 2,958 and max of ₦ 80,592). The total employment effect was 0.2, with a 0.1 direct effect on employment; zero indirect and induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 855,391; the mean value-added was ₦ 285,130.7k; the median value added was ₦ 76,565; the range of the value-added was ₦ 636,891 (with a min of ₦ 70,968 and max of ₦ 707,859). The total output was ₦ 965,264; the mean output was ₦ 32,175.7k; the median output was ₦ 88,136; the range of the output was ₦ 705,572 (with a min of ₦ 85,778 and max of ₦ 791,350).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 11, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 86,312; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 8631.2k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 334; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 81,626 (with a min of ₦ 26 and max of ₦ 81,652). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 840,464; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 84,046.4k; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 5,746.5k; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 715,265 (with a min of ₦ 1,899 and max of ₦ 717,164). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 942,803; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 94280.3k; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 7810.5k; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 798,298 (with a min of ₦ 3,455 and max of ₦ 801,753).

4.2. 2016 Expenditure and Donation Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2016 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 12, in the AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 224,357; the mean labor income was ₦ 74,785.67k; the median labor income was ₦ 10,104; the range of the labor income was ₦ 199,081 (with a min of ₦ 7,586 and max of ₦ 206,667). The total employment effect was 0.4, with a 0.2 direct effect on employment; 0.1 indirect effects on employment; 0.1 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 2,193,524; the mean value-added was ₦ 731,174.7k; the median value added was ₦ 196,339; the range of the value-added was ₦ 1,633,213 (with a min of ₦ 219,966 and max of ₦ 1,815,199). The total output was ₦ 2,475,277; the mean output was ₦ 825,092.3k; the median output was ₦ 226,011; the range of the output was ₦ 1,809,334 (with a min of ₦ 219,966 and max of ₦ 2,029,300). The economic impact of the AOIF donations shows total labor income of donations was ₦ 27,640; the mean labor income of donations was ₦ 9,213.33k; the median labor income of donations was ₦ 1,245; the range of the labor income of donations was ₦ 24,525 (with a min of ₦ 935 and max of ₦ 25,460). The total employment effect of donations was 0.1 and a zero direct, indirect, and induced employment effect on the economy. The total value added of donations was ₦ 270,232; the mean value-added of donations was ₦ 90,077.33k; the median value-added of donations was ₦ 24,188; the range of the value-added of donations was ₦ 201,204 (with a min of ₦ 22,420 and max of ₦ 223,624). The total output of donations was ₦ 304,942; the mean output of donations was ₦ 101,647.3k; the median output of donations was ₦ 27,843; the range of the output was ₦ 222,901 (with a min of ₦ 27,099 and max of ₦ 250,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 13, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 221,334; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 22,133.4k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 856; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 209,317 (with a min of ₦ 67 and max of ₦ 209,384). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,155,246; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 215,524.6k; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 14,735.5k; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,834,190 (with a min of ₦ 4,871 and max of ₦ 1,839,061). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,417,680; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 241,768k; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 20,029; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,047,117 (with a min of ₦ 8,860 and max of ₦ 2,055,977). On the aggregate donations level of the top ten industries, the total donations labor income was ₦ 27,267; the mean donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,726.7k; the median donations labor income of the top ten

industries was ₦ 105; the range of the donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 25,787 (with a min of ₦ 8 and max of ₦ 25,795). The total donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 265,517; the mean donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 26,551.7k; the median donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,815.5k; the range donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 225,964 (with a min of ₦ 600 and max of ₦ 226,564). The total donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 297,845; the mean donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 29,784.5k; the median donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,467.5k; the range of donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 252,195 (with a min of ₦ 1,091 and max of ₦ 253,286).

Figure 5: Total Expenditure

Source: (AOIFFR, 2022)

Figure five shows an upward trend of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the form of donations flowing into the Nigerian economy.

4.3. 2017 Expenditure and Donation Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2017 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 14, in the AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 268,725; the mean labor income was ₦ 89,574.67k; the median labor income was ₦ 12,102; the range of the labor income was ₦ 238,450 (with a min of ₦ 9,086 and max of ₦ 247,536). The total employment effect was 0.5, with a 0.3 direct effect on employment; 0.1 indirect effects on employment; 0.1 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 2,174,162; the mean value-added was ₦ 875,767.7k; the median value added was ₦ 235,166; the range of the value-added was ₦ 1,956,187 (with a min of ₦ 217,975 and max of ₦ 2,174,162). The total output was ₦ 2,964,774; the mean output was ₦ 988,257.7k; the median output was ₦ 270,705; the range of the output was ₦ 2,167,138 (with a min of ₦ 263,465 and max of ₦ 2,430,603). The economic impact of the AOIF donations shows total labor income of donations was ₦ 71,863; the mean labor income of donations was ₦ 23,954.33k; the median labor income of donations was ₦ 3,236; the range of the labor income of donations was ₦ 63,767 (with a min of ₦ 2,430 and max of ₦ 66,197). The total employment effect of donations was 0.1, 0.1 direct effect, and a zero indirect and induced employment effect on the economy. The total value added of donations was ₦ 702,602; the mean value-added of donations was ₦ 234,201; the median value-added of donations was ₦ 62,889; the range of the value-added of donations was ₦ 523,130 (with a min of ₦ 58,292 and max of ₦ 581,422). The total output of donations was ₦ 792,850; the mean output of donations was ₦ 264,283.3k; the median output of donations was ₦ 72,393; the range of the output was ₦ 57,953 (with a min of ₦ 70,457 and max of ₦ 650,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 15, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 265,104; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 26,510.4k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,025.5k; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 250,710 (with a min of ₦ 80 and max of ₦ 250,790). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,581,456; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 258,145.6k; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 17,649; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,196,910 (with a min of ₦ 5,834 and max of ₦ 2,462,556). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,895,787; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 289,578.7k; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 23,989.5k; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,451,944 (with a min of ₦ 10,612 and max of ₦ 2,462,556). On the aggregate donations level of the top ten industries, the total donations labor income was ₦ 70,894; the mean donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 7,089.4k; the median donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 274; the range of the donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 67,046 (with a min of ₦ 21 and max of ₦ 67,067). The total donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 690,341; the mean donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 69,034.1k; the median donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 4,720; the range donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 587,505 (with a min of ₦ 1,560 and max of ₦ 589,065). The total donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 774,403; the mean donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 77,440.3k; the median donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 6,415.5k; the range of donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 655,707 (with a min of ₦ 2,838 and max of ₦ 658,545).

4.4. 2018 Expenditure and Donation Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2018 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 16, in the AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 487,601; the mean labor income was ₦ 162,533.3k; the median labor income was ₦ 21,959; the range of the labor income was ₦ 432,667 (with a min of ₦ 16,487 and max of ₦ 449,154). The total employment effect was 1, with a 0.5 direct effect on employment; 0.2 indirect effects on employment; 0.2 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 4,767,239; the mean value-added was ₦ 1,589,080; the median value added was ₦ 426,708; the range of the value-added was ₦ 3,549,501 (with a min of ₦ 395,515 and max of ₦ 3,945,016). The total output was ₦ 5,379,579; the mean output was ₦ 1,793,193; the median output was ₦ 491,194; the range of the output was ₦ 3,932,269 (with a min of ₦ 478,058 and max of ₦ 4,410,327). The economic impact of the AOIF donations shows total labor income of donations was ₦ 101,051; the mean labor income of donations was ₦ 33,683.67k; the median labor income of donations was ₦ 4,551; the range of the labor income of donations was ₦ 89,666 (with a min of ₦ 3,417 and max of ₦ 93,083). The total employment effect of donations was 0.2, 0.1 direct employment impact, zero indirect, and induced employment effect on the economy. The total value added of donations was ₦ 987,967; the mean value-added of donations was ₦ 329,322; the median value-added of donations was ₦ 88,431; the range of the value-added of donations was ₦ 735,601 (with a min of ₦ 81,967 and max of ₦ 817,568). The total output of donations was ₦ 1,114,869; the mean output of donations was ₦ 371,623; the median output of donations was ₦ 101,796; the range of the output was ₦ 814,927 (with a min of ₦ 99,073 and max of ₦ 914,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 17, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 481,029; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 48,102.9k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,860; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 454,914 (with a min of ₦ 145 and max of ₦ 455,059). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 4,684,048; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 468,404.8k; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 32,024.5k; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 3,986,291 (with a min of ₦ 10,586 and max of ₦ 3,996,877). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 5,254,403; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 525,440.3k; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 43529.5k; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 4,449,050 (with a min of ₦ 19,255 and max of ₦ 4,468,305). On the aggregate donations level of the top ten industries, the total donations labor income was ₦ 99,689; the mean donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 9,968.9k; the median donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 385.5k; the range of the donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 94,277 (with a min of ₦ 30 and max of ₦ 94,307). The total donations' value-added of the top ten industries

was ₺ 970,725; the mean donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₺ 97,072.5k; the median donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₺ 6,636.5k; the range donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₺ 826,122 (with a min of ₺ 2,194 and max of ₺ 828,316). The total donations' output of the top ten industries was ₺ 1,088,925; the mean donations' output of the top ten industries was ₺ 108,892.5k; the median donations' output of the top ten industries was ₺ 9,021; the range of donations' output of the top ten industries was ₺ 922,025 (with a min of ₺ 3,990 and max of ₺ 926,015).

Figure 6: Change in Total Expenditure

Source: (AOIFFR, 2022)

Figure six shows the percentage change in the FDI flow into the nation due to the AOIF activities in the country.

4.5. 2019 Expenditure and Donation Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2019 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 18, in the AS) shows that the total labor income was ₺ 323,179; the mean labor income was ₺ 107,726.3k; the median labor income was ₺ 14,555; the range of the labor income was ₺ 286,768 (with a min of ₺ 10,928 and max of ₺ 297,696). The total employment effect was 0.6, with a 0.4 direct effect on employment; 0.1 indirect effects on employment; 0.2 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₺ 3,159,691; the mean value-added was ₺ 1,053,230; the median value added was ₺ 282,819; the range of the value-added was ₺ 2,352,583 (with a min of ₺ 262,144 and max of ₺ 2,614,727). The total output was ₺ 3,565,545; the mean output was ₺ 1,188,515; the median output was ₺ 325,560; the range of the output was ₺ 2,606,279 (with a min of ₺ 316,853 and max of ₺ 2,923,132). The economic impact of the AOIF donations shows total labor income of donations was ₺ 132,671; the mean labor income of donations was ₺ 44,223.67k; the median labor income of donations was ₺ 5,975; the range of the labor income of donations was ₺ 117,724 (with a min of ₺ 4,486 and max of ₺ 122,210). The total employment effect of donations was 0.3 and a 0.1 direct, indirect, and induced employment effect on the economy. The total value added of donations was ₺ 1,297,112; the mean value-added of donations was ₺ 432,370.7k; the median value-added of donations was ₺ 116,103; the range of the value-added of donations was ₺ 965,779 (with a min of ₺ 107,615 and max of ₺ 1,073,394). The total output of donations was ₺ 1,463,722; the mean output of donations was ₺ 487,907.3k; the median output of donations was ₺ 133,648; the range of the output was ₺ 1,069,926 (with a min of ₺ 130,074 and max of ₺ 1,200,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 19, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₺ 318,823; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₺ 31,882.3k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₺ 1,233; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₺ 301,514 (with a min of ₺ 96 and max of ₺ 301,610). The total value added of the top ten

industries was ₦ 3,104,553; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 310,455.3k; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 21,226; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,642,084 (with a min of ₦ 7,016 and max of ₦ 2,649,100). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 3,482,581; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 348,258.1k; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 28,851; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,948,798 (with a min of ₦ 12,762 and max of ₦ 2,961,560). On the aggregate donations level of the top ten industries, the total donations labor income was ₦ 130,881; the mean donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 13,088.1k; the median donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 506.5k; the range of the donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 123,777 (with a min of ₦ 39 and max of ₦ 123,816). The total donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,274,475; the mean donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 127,447.5k; the median donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 8,713.5k; the range donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,084,625 (with a min of ₦ 2,880 and max of ₦ 1,087,505). The total donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,429,663; the mean donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 142,966.3k; the median donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 11,844; the range of donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,210,536 (with a min of ₦ 5,239 and max of ₦ 1,215,775).

4.6. 2020 Expenditure and Donation Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2020 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 20, in the AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 127,146; the mean labor income was ₦ 42,382; the median labor income was ₦ 5,726; the range of the labor income was ₦ 112,822 (with a min of ₦ 4,299 and max of ₦ 117,121). The total employment effect was 0.3, with a 0.1 direct effect on employment; 0.1 indirect effects on employment; 0.1 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 1,243,095; the mean value-added was ₦ 414,365; the median value added was ₦ 111,268; the range of the value-added was ₦ 925,559 (with a min of ₦ 103,134 and max of ₦ 1,028,693). The total output was ₦ 1,402,767; the mean output was ₦ 467,589; the median output was ₦ 128,083; the range of the output was ₦ 1,025,370 (with a min of ₦ 124,657 and max of ₦ 1,150,027). The economic impact of the AOIF donations shows total labor income of donations was ₦ 995,031; the mean labor income of donations was ₦ 331,677; the median labor income of donations was ₦ 44,812; the range of the labor income of donations was ₦ 882,929 (with a min of ₦ 33,645 and max of ₦ 916,574). The total employment effect of donations was 2; 1.1 direct, 0.4 indirect; 0.5 induced employment effect on the economy. The total value added of donations was ₦ 9,728,338; the mean value-added of donations was ₦ 3,242,779; the median value-added of donations was ₦ 870,769; the range of the value-added of donations was ₦ 7,243,341 (with a min of ₦ 807,114 and max of ₦ 8,050,455). The total output of donations was ₦ 10,977,920; the mean output of donations was ₦ 3,659,307; the median output of donations was ₦ 1,002,364; the range of the output was ₦ 8,024,444 (with a min of ₦ 975,556 and max of ₦ 9,000,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 21, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 125,432; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 12,543.2k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 485; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 118,622 (with a min of ₦ 38 and max of ₦ 118,660). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,221,402; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 122,140.2k; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 8,350.5k; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,039,457 (with a min of ₦ 2,760 and max of ₦ 1,042,217). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,370,128; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 137,012.8k; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 11,351; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,160,124 (with a min of ₦ 5,021 and max of ₦ 1,165,145). On the aggregate donations level of the top ten industries, the total donations labor income was ₦ 981,620; the mean donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 98,162; the median donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 3796.5k; the range of the donations labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 928,328 (with a min of ₦ 295 and max of ₦ 928,623). The total donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 9,558,572; the mean donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 955,857.2k; the median donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 65,352k; the range donations' value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 8,134,685 (with a min of ₦ 21,602 and max of ₦ 8,156,287). The total donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 10,722,476; the mean donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,072,248; the median donations' output of

the top ten industries was ₦ 88,829.5k; the range of donations' output of the top ten industries was ₦ 9,079,022 (with a min of ₦ 39,292 and max of ₦ 9,118,314).

Source: (AOIFFR, 2022)

Figure seven shows the total donations to public schools made by the AOIF from 2015 to 2021. The pie chart shows 2020 at 80%, 2019 at 11%, 2017 at 6%, 2016 at 2%, 2018 at 1% and 2021 & 2015 at 0%.

4.7. 2021 Expenditure and Donation Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2021 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 22, AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 1,658,385; the mean labor income was ₦ 552,795; the median labor income was ₦ 74,686; the range of the labor income was ₦ 1,471,547 (with a min of ₦ 56,076 and max of ₦ 1,527,623). The total employment effect was 3.3, with a 1.8 direct effect on employment; 0.7 indirect, and 0.8 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 16,213,895; the mean value-added was ₦ 5,404,632; the median value added was ₦ 1,451,281; the range of the value-added was ₦ 1,471,547 (with a min of ₦ 56,076 and max of ₦ 1,527,623). The total output was ₦ 18,296,532; the mean output was ₦ 6,098,844; the median output was ₦ 1,670,606; the range of the output was ₦ 13,374,074 (with a min of ₦ 1,625,926 and max of ₦ 15,000,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 23, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 1,636,033; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 163,603.3k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 6,327.5; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,547,213 (with a min of ₦ 492 and max of ₦ 1,547,705). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 15,930,953; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,593,095; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 108,920; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 13,557,808 (with a min of ₦ 36,003 and max of ₦ 13,593,811). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 17,870,793; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,787,079; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 148,049; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 15,131,703 (with a min of ₦ 65,487 and max of ₦ 15,197,190).

Figure 8: Estimated Cost

Source: (AOIFFR, 2022)

Figure-eight shows the AOIF unpublished estimated financial project activities that would have helped create new jobs and boost the Nigerian economy. However, due to the unfavorable business environment plaguing the nation, the foundation moved its business activities to a more favorable business environment.

4.8. Anticipated Transactional Cost Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF unpublished activities in the year 2022 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 24, in the AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 1,151,431; the mean labor income was ₦ 383,810; the median labor income was ₦ 382,567; the range of the labor income was ₦ 665,153 (with a min of ₦ 51,855 and max of ₦ 717,008). The total employment effect was 32.7, with a 28.8 direct effect on employment, 3.3 indirect, and 0.6 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 49,042,545; the mean value-added was ₦ 38,720,827; the median value added was ₦ 9,387,742; the range of the value-added was ₦ 37,786,851 (with a min of ₦ 933,976 and max of ₦ 38,720,827). The total output was ₦ 60,503,444; the mean output was ₦ 20,167,815; the median output was ₦ 10,343,528; the range of the output was ₦ 47,840,084 (with a min of ₦ 1,159,916 and max of ₦ 49,000,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 26, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 1,080,923; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 108,092.3k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 22,913.5k; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 716,556 (with a min of ₦ 583 and max of ₦ 717,139). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 48,391,976; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 4,839,198; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 365,635; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 38,685,256 (with a min of ₦ 42,640 and max of ₦ 38,727,896). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 59,604,129; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 5,960,413; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 440,959.5k; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 48,878,394 (with a min of ₦ 130,552 and max of ₦ 49,008,946).

4.9. Anticipated Nayomee Project's Cost Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2022 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 24, AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 10,879,202; the mean labor income was ₦ 3,626,401; the median labor income was ₦ 1,238,822; the range of the labor income was ₦ 8,660,478 (with a min of ₦ 489,951 and max of ₦ 9,150,429). The total employment effect was 31.3, with a 12.6 direct effect on

employment, 13.3 indirect, and 5.4 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 105,232,221; the mean value-added was ₦ 35,077,407; the median value added was ₦ 26,269,585; the range of the value-added was ₦ 61,313,431 (with a min of ₦ 8,824,603 and max of ₦ 70,138,034). The total output was ₦ 142,568,360; the mean output was ₦ 47,522,787; the median output was ₦ 30,608,987; the range of the output was ₦ 90,040,625 (with a min of ₦ 10,959,374 and max of ₦ 100,999,999).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 25, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 10,503,644; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,050,364; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 132,943.5k; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 9,153,251 (with a min of ₦ 6,245 and max of ₦ 9,159,496). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 105,232,221; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 10,054,207; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,089,431; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 69,842,850 (with a min of ₦ 364,683 and max of ₦ 70,207,533). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 136,425,010; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 13,642,501; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 2,597,650; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 100,660,635 (with a min of ₦ 439,444 and max of ₦ 101,100,079).

4.10. Anticipated Evergreen & Woodbury Project's Cost Economic Impact Results

Based on (AOIFFR, 2022), the economic impact of the AOIF activities in the year 2022 based on our empirical analysis (see Table 24 AS) shows that the total labor income was ₦ 5,385,744; the mean labor income was ₦ 1,795,248; the median labor income was ₦ 613,278; the range of the labor income was ₦ 4,287,365 (with a min of ₦ 242,550 and max of ₦ 4,529,915). The total employment effect was 15.5, with a 6.2 direct effect on employment, 6.6 indirect, and 2.7 induced effect on employment. The total value added was ₦ 52,095,159; the mean value-added was ₦ 17,365,053; the median value added was ₦ 13,004,745; the range of the value-added was ₦ 30,353,184 (with a min of ₦ 4,368,615 and max of ₦ 34,721,799). The total output was ₦ 70,578,396; the mean output was ₦ 23,526,132; the median output was ₦ 15,152,964; the range of the output was ₦ 44,574,567 (with a min of ₦ 5,425,433 and max of ₦ 50,000,000).

Based on the AOIF activities, the top ten industry gainers are (see Table 25, in the AS). On the aggregate level of the top ten industries, the total labor income was ₦ 5,199,823; the mean labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 519,982.3k; the median labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 65,813.5k; the range of the labor income of the top ten industries was ₦ 4,531,313 (with a min of ₦ 3,091 and max of ₦ 4,534,404). The total value added of the top ten industries was ₦ 49,773,299; the mean value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 4,977,330; the median value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,034,372; the range value-added of the top ten industries was ₦ 34,575,668 (with a min of ₦ 180,536 and max of ₦ 34,756,204). The total output of the top ten industries was ₦ 67,537,134; the mean output of the top ten industries was ₦ 6,753,713; the median output of the top ten industries was ₦ 1,285,965; the range output of the top ten industries was ₦ 49,831,997 (with a min of ₦ 217,547 and max of ₦ 50,049,544).

5. Conclusion

An economic impact analysis story will not wholly show the picture to understand the Nigerian business environment. A psychologist, sociologist, and political scientist analysis is also needed. According to (Landes, 1998), the most significant resource a nation and its people should have, is trust; because the lack of that variable in the equation of doing business will inevitably lead to a hostile business environment. According to the (Boston University Global Development Policy Center (BUGDPC), 2022), in 2020, the Chinese loans to Africa database, which the BUGDPC manages, recorded eleven new loans to different African countries [with Nigeria making 5% of the pie] according to (Hwang et al., 2022).

Nigeria has borrowed over \$6.5 billion from China since 2002 to build power plants and transportation systems and, in recent news, to pay for its state's works. The nation's infrastructure backbone II project currently uses about 55% of its annual revenue to service debts which are projected to increase to 96% within the next decade. Today,

Chinese loans represent 10% of Nigeria's debt stock and account for 80% of bilateral loans instead of multilateral institutions. The effects of COVID-19 on African economies led to a 77% reduction in the \$8.2 billion agreement Chinese lending capacity may explain such a drastic drop in Chinese lending amounts to Africa in 2020 and currently moving away from investing in Nigeria (Nyabiage, 2022).

The word motivation seems to be thrown around when inspiring young entrepreneurs. Nigeria is estimated to be the most populated nation by 2030, with youths making up about 65% of its population. Hence the interesting question is, what motivates a nation to be trustworthy like Japan, and what makes a nation to be corrupt. Understanding the question well enough that you put one's-self as a Japanese or Nigerian national may be the key for nations like Nigeria to create a more friendly business environment; which in turn will translate to economic growth and development as it is well known that Japan, when compared to Nigerian, is a natural resource-poor nation but in comparison with Real Gross Domestic Product Japan is a wealthier nation.

Evidence suggests that ordinary Nigerians can be as trustworthy as Japanese nationals, but how do we best achieve this? Because this is fundamentally an issue of individual psychology, and one can not be motivated enough to put their country in order to the degree that is necessary [reducing brain drain, massive out-migration, and increased local corruption at every level of the economy] merely by attracted to the thing the western world [Norway, Finland, and Estonia] have or a potential African euphoria that might emerge as a consequence of Afriacaniess [a vision of heaven] no, a nation needs also be terrified of the hellish conditions its citizen faces of corruption is not reduced and the future of its next-generation on the world stage. Hence the solution is "YOU [the everyday Nigerian that says no to participating in corruption in their little (area/office) of power]" not them but YOU. Because if YOU don't right and take yourself with enough seriousness, the nation will continue to be one with a hostile business environment.

Generally, as a country that pried itself as a religious country in its culture and beliefs, people from the outside might say the nation is not really good at believing in what they say they believe¹ (speaking from the laws of the Torah and the New Testament beliefs). Hence one might argue with solid evidence that the nation is full of conflict and doubts and might not be able to articulate its culture, but its people's way of life is the bedrock of their culture. Hence the ways of the Nigerian government are synonymous with the ways of the Nigerian people at the individual level. Some argue that *"rights are attributed to YOU by the government, but the government is dependant on your actions [hence that statement of the Nigerian people (our government is corrupt)."* To believe that statement is also to believe that the state is an entity and the people are subordinates to the government. This can not be so in a democracy; *"the state is dependant on the individual to the proportion that the individual is dependant on the government,"* hence making the individual and the government one. The failure to see Nigerians within the Nigerian system as one is a step in the wrong direction in solving the country's corruption issues and creating a friendly business environment that will promote economic growth and development; because the individual is the active agent of the state (eyes, hands, mouth, and sense organs of the government).

Declaration of Competing Interest

The author declares that they have no financial interest that could have appeared to directly or indirectly influence the work reported in this paper.

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¹ The divine sovereign individual.

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Appendix:

Table 5: The Production Account of the Nigerian Economy 2021

Industry Code	Description	Employment	Output ₦	Employee Compensation ₦	Proprietor Income ₦	Other Property Type Income ₦	Tax on Production and Imports ₦
3000	Total	57,833,308.60	44,705,258,363,281	1,722,474,518,005	566,252,337,265	32,793,545,446,289	24,189,853,139
3001	Agriculture	14,369,937.00	2,468,390,750,000	4,461,256,348	4,015,268,555	612,179,375,000	(173,294,128)
3002	Fishing	156,437.20	45,030,437,500	782,185,974	199,231,476	35,102,457,031	7,093,147
3003	Mining and Quarrying	2,730,308.00	3,323,925,250,000	21,027,123,047	17,120,103,516	1,958,215,000,000	4,676,562,012
3004	Food and beverages	622,433.30	1,396,554,875,000	22,300,917,969	9,257,606,445	900,987,187,500	1,321,530,640
3005	Textiles and wearing apparel	255,813.30	222,037,843,750	9,165,431,641	2,303,702,637	153,209,062,500	122,806,641
3006	Wood and paper	529,971.50	444,207,593,750	18,988,138,672	4,878,076,660	354,374,687,500	246,928,253
3007	Petroleum, Chemical, and Non-metal mfg.	951,748.50	1,315,054,750,000	34,099,824,219	11,624,273,438	1,054,070,250,000	1,925,015,747
3008	Metal products	573,480.80	358,452,781,250	20,547,017,578	4,578,950,195	268,071,937,500	346,151,459
3009	Electrical and machinery	1,611,277.50	1,161,742,875,000	57,729,824,219	13,176,477,539	834,692,000,000	433,713,318
3010	Transport equipment	532,395.50	594,186,250,000	19,074,988,281	5,377,593,750	351,898,750,000	170,056,488
3011	Other manufacturing	259,879.70	242,399,546,875	9,311,125,977	2,615,573,730	160,224,062,500	112,877,800
3012	Recycling	457,500.60	101,882,968,750	1,152,485,840	78,491,653	13,303,948,242	15,993,661
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	7,747,352.00	714,770,562,500	19,516,289,063	11,772,144,531	560,155,875,000	1,724,247,314
3014	Construction	573,480.80	1,540,281,750,000	114,411,054,688	25,135,867,188	929,758,437,500	321,706,482
3015	Maintenance and repair	280,635.30	100,227,640,625	5,174,949,707	1,493,704,590	69,572,023,438	292,449,036
3016	Wholesale Trade	5,620,884.50	1,945,014,125,000	103,649,804,688	26,986,919,922	1,467,793,875,000	4,401,108,887
3017	Retail Trade	6,195,669.50	2,601,097,250,000	114,248,914,063	35,396,062,500	1,474,668,125,000	6,882,103,027
3018	Hotels and restaurants	255,813.30	1,612,281,125,000	68,624,554,688	20,268,449,219	859,927,187,500	2,800,576,660
3019	Transport	529,971.50	1,351,310,000,000	70,394,031,250	15,319,787,109	833,171,812,500	965,149,414
3020	Post and telecommunications	1,142,569.00	1,585,894,750,000	53,897,160,156	20,334,052,734	1,295,790,000,000	923,219,971
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	9,497,830.00	13,811,901,000,000	233,043,187,500	129,677,648,438	12,952,378,000,000	(5,587,405,273)
3022	Public Administration	532,395.50	2,363,247,250,000	285,745,656,250	94,258,789,063	1,390,981,750,000	1,044,419,678
3023	Education, Health, and other services	1,868,165.40	5,178,001,000,000	422,495,000,000	104,840,570,313	4,103,201,750,000	1,158,900,024
3024	Private Households	226,039.80	49,607,050,781	11,077,000,000	4,498,473,145	21,976,345,703	31,766,306
3025	Others	311,319.30	177,758,937,500	1,556,596,191	1,044,518,921	137,841,546,875	26,176,577

Source: (Implan 11 software and Database for Nigeria, 2022)

Table 6: The Social Account of the Nigerian Economy 2021

Code	Description	Industry Commodity Production ₦	Institutional Commodity Production ₦	Total Commodity Supply ₦	Net Commodity Supply ₦	Intermediate Commodity Demand ₦	Institutional Commodity Demand ₦	Total Gross Commodity Demand ₦	Domestic Supply/ Demand Ratio	Avg RP C	Avg RSC
3000	Total	44,705,258,363,281	(2,688,946,454)	44,702,569,416,827	39,669,734,276,934	9,598,792,278,992	33,343,992,374,877	42,942,788,653,870	-	-	-
3001	Agriculture	2,468,390,750,000	(177,980,423)	2,468,212,769,577	2,263,733,457,077	2,010,239,264,570	283,854,918	2,294,092,643,918	98.68%	98.68%	91.72%
3002	Fishing	45,030,437,500	(13,491,746)	45,016,945,754	43,807,105,178	37,231,801,382	10,626,413,917	47,858,215,298	91.54%	91.54%	97.31%
3003	Mining and Quarrying	3,323,925,250,000	(74,973,648)	3,323,850,276,352	6,649,276,352	6,625,447,189	8,496,330,551	15,121,777,740	43.97%	43.97%	0.20%
3004	Food and beverages	1,396,554,875,000	(208,727,707)	1,396,346,147,293	1,335,506,412,918	115,195,529,480	1,348,998,630,126	1,464,194,159,606	91.21%	91.21%	95.64%
3005	Textiles and wearing apparel	222,037,843,750	(33,319,256)	222,004,524,494	177,161,801,838	15,611,599,941	193,389,536,125	209,001,136,066	84.77%	84.77%	79.80%
3006	Wood and paper	444,207,593,750	(54,844,383)	444,152,749,367	428,793,571,632	389,218,790,839	136,834,791,893	526,053,582,732	81.51%	81.51%	96.54%
3007	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	1,315,054,750,000	(70,227,440)	1,314,984,522,560	960,498,522,560	573,550,987,810	756,083,720,848	1,329,634,708,659	72.24%	72.24%	73.04%
3008	Metal products	358,452,781,250	(169,012,543)	358,283,768,707	343,637,556,793	430,703,113,739	49,012,651,947	479,715,765,686	71.63%	71.63%	95.91%
3009	Electrical and machinery	1,161,742,875,000	(426,447,113)	1,161,316,427,887	1,129,655,257,965	491,116,567,196	1,108,424,290,863	1,599,540,858,059	70.62%	70.62%	97.28%
3010	Transport equipment	594,186,250,000	(580,486,938)	593,605,763,062	580,064,094,116	82,016,621,381	736,626,088,501	818,642,709,882	70.86%	70.86%	97.72%
3011	Other manufacturing	242,399,546,875	(58,812,054)	242,340,734,821	236,975,717,243	63,219,907,199	226,482,288,616	289,702,195,816	81.80%	81.80%	97.79%
3012	Recycling	101,882,968,750	(119,094,223)	101,763,874,527	97,534,996,597	1,782,929,129	98,675,883,053	100,458,812,182	97.09%	97.09%	95.85%
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	714,770,562,500	(160,046)	714,770,402,454	708,919,408,313	219,184,951,584	549,737,655,263	768,922,606,848	92.20%	92.20%	99.18%
3014	Construction	1,540,281,750,000	(38,897)	1,540,281,711,103	1,504,795,933,759	240,271,707,866	1,445,949,780,108	1,686,221,487,974	89.24%	89.24%	97.70%
3015	Maintenance and repair	100,227,640,625	(2,701,929)	100,224,938,696	94,430,241,430	6,761,515,691	93,212,373,194	99,973,888,885	94.46%	94.46%	94.22%
3016	Wholesale Trade	1,945,014,125,000	(190,514,328)	1,944,823,610,672	1,880,817,216,141	501,755,487,610	1,521,737,164,719	2,023,492,652,329	92.95%	92.95%	96.71%
3017	Retail Trade	2,601,097,250,000	(32,665)	2,601,097,217,335	2,554,805,721,241	54,521,095,301	2,554,191,886,791	2,608,712,982,092	97.93%	97.93%	98.22%

3018	Hotels and restaurants	1,612,281,125,000	(30,473)	1,612,281,094,527	1,498,039,414,839	31,718,184,946	1,562,548,271,535	1,594,266,456,481	93.96%	93.96%	92.91%
3019	Transport	1,351,310,000,000	(24,375,132)	1,351,285,624,868	937,067,531,118	385,955,646,861	738,704,006,968	1,124,659,653,829	83.32%	83.32%	69.35%
3020	Post and telecommunication	1,585,894,750,000	(2,175,288)	1,585,892,574,712	1,481,399,621,587	416,787,923,949	1,140,093,836,421	1,556,881,760,370	95.15%	95.15%	93.41%
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	13,811,901,000,000	(481,154,236)	13,811,419,845,764	13,758,686,240,295	3,429,157,042,684	10,628,106,302,673	14,057,263,345,357	97.88%	97.88%	99.62%
3022	Public Administration	2,363,247,250,000	(24,591)	2,363,247,225,409	2,347,405,312,323	2,163,830,302	2,680,704,059,748	2,682,867,890,049	87.50%	87.50%	99.33%
3023	Education, Health, and other services	5,178,001,000,000	(262,697)	5,178,000,737,303	5,074,350,651,365	49,327,865,230	5,275,884,063,479	5,325,211,928,708	95.29%	95.29%	98.00%
3024	Private Households	49,607,050,781	(17,008)	49,607,033,773	48,397,253,988	15,820,875	57,086,064,175	57,101,885,051	84.76%	84.76%	97.56%
3025	Others	177,758,937,500	(41,689)	177,758,895,811	176,601,960,264	44,662,646,239	138,532,904,015	183,195,550,254	96.40%	96.40%	99.35%

Source: (Implan 11 software and Database for Nigeria, 2022)

Where:

RPC = A Regional Purchase Coefficient (RPC) is the proportion of the total demand for a Commodity by all users in the Study Area that is supplied by producers located within the Study Area. Average RPC is the proportion of local demand for the Commodity that is currently met by local production.

RSC = The RSC, also known as the Local Use Ratio, indicates the proportion of the local supply of a Commodity that goes to meet local demands. It is calculated by dividing the Local Use of Local Supply by the Total Local Commodity Supply. Average RSC is the proportion of the local supply of the Commodity that goes to meet local demand.

Table 7: The Industry Account of the Nigerian Economy 2021

Code	Description	Household Demand ₦	Federal Government Demand ₦	Capital ₦	Inventory ₦	Foreign Exports ₦
3000	Total	24,659,713,678,178	3,554,503,279,812	2,678,719,313,926	2,206,621,819	5,033,015,641,993
3001	Agriculture	277,278,838,271	589,750,581	2,072,937,978	175,637,759	204,494,057,304
3002	Fishing	9,442,222,741	275,006,481	240,047	12,353,396	1,210,203,170
3003	Mining and Quarrying	3,533,823,314	74,876,402	94,382,906	2,967,800	3,317,275,823,665
3004	Food and beverages	1,230,428,602,580	141,888	168,202	190,411,127	60,848,828,781
3005	Textiles and wearing apparel	159,320,706,487	28,225,399	4,575,904,069	28,247,623	44,849,452,817
3006	Wood and paper	108,816,248,146	1,287,077,543	1,401,673,697	44,709,938	15,361,074,300
3007	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	540,714,486,243	2,342,462,974	3,099,539,584	50,733,449	354,504,931,511
3008	Metal products	19,509,692,485	974,455,561	14,520,802,462	121,126,840	14,653,120,945
3009	Electrical and machinery	327,159,239,571	66,505,157,455	389,132,243,812	301,283,409	31,672,796,223
3010	Transport equipment	363,235,215,954	45,118,557,348	113,694,658,561	411,716,741	13,554,911,340
3011	Other manufacturing	149,748,781,695	8,075,909,422	27,434,130,392	48,119,797	5,366,319,578
3012	Recycling	94,897,730,640	902,411,930	172,359	115,763,350	4,233,826,984
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	506,838,285,482	141,778	185,144	147,557	5,850,995,451
3014	Construction	18,187,108,736	172,657,369,594	1,099,531,288,709	34,712	35,485,778,240
3015	Maintenance and repair	84,549,355,158	287,106,028	3,207,018,409	2,552,174	5,794,853,483
3016	Wholesale Trade	1,241,559,359,588	17,793,594,547	155,048,757,773	177,098,607	64,012,664,578
3017	Retail Trade	2,464,937,887,310	934,024,806	35,539,354,211	31,990	46,291,496,675
3018	Hotels and restaurants	1,468,232,371,611	3,130,511	179,201	28,634	114,241,681,847
3019	Transport	589,377,873,514	8,501,066,212	17,600,759,074	20,309,750	414,225,565,613
3020	Post and telecommunications	979,650,227,795	8,308,574,177	96,859,400,019	2,069,827	104,493,096,453
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	9,943,920,266,978	92,754,644,711	365,581,225,025	470,950,898	52,735,442,572
3022	Public Administration	71,417,536,498	1,982,946,902,918	291,147,608,237	21,516	15,841,913,251
3023	Education, Health, and other services	3,825,903,673,260	1,143,266,508,369	58,176,357,372	250,322	103,650,091,196
3024	Private Households	47,507,742,934	875,992,209	111,883	14,415	1,209,780,200
3025	Others	133,546,401,189	190,969	214,800	40,189	1,156,935,818
10001	Households	-	-	-	-	-
11001	Government	-	-	-	-	-
14001	Capital	-	-	-	-	-
14002	Inventory Additions/Deletions	-	-	-	-	-

Source: (Implan 11 software and Database for Nigeria, 2022)

Table 8: Multiplier by Top 25 sectors of the Economy in Nigeria

Code	Description	Direct Effect	Indirect Effects	Induced Effects	Total Effects	Type I Multiplier	Type SAM Multiplier
3001	Agriculture	1	2.26552 2	0.019125	3.284647	3.265522	3.284647
3002	Fishing	1	0.21416 5	0.030517	1.244682	1.214165	1.244682
3003	Mining and Quarrying	1	0.41285	0.032414	1.445264	1.41285	1.445264
3004	Food and beverages	1	0.67789 8	0.034659	1.712557	1.677898	1.712557
3005	Textiles and wearing apparel	1	0.29362 6	0.064353	1.357979	1.293626	1.357979
3006	Wood and paper	1	0.20831 6	0.062055	1.270371	1.208316	1.270371
3007	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	1	0.16715	0.043117	1.210267	1.16715	1.210267
3008	Metal products	1	0.18217 9	0.081237	1.263416	1.182179	1.263416
3009	Electrical and machinery	1	0.21734 6	0.073315	1.29066	1.217346	1.29066
3010	Transport equipment	1	0.33583 6	0.060775	1.396611	1.335836	1.396611
3011	Other manufacturing	1	0.27966 4	0.065264	1.344928	1.279664	1.344928
3012	Recycling	1	0.78922 2	0.054936	1.844158	1.789222	1.844158
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	1	0.17374 5	0.053305	1.22705	1.173745	1.22705
3014	Construction	1	0.30305 9	0.108509	1.411568	1.303059	1.411568
3015	Maintenance and repair	1	0.24465 6	0.07947	1.324126	1.244656	1.324126
3016	Wholesale Trade	1	0.18046 1	0.077406	1.257867	1.180461	1.257867
3017	Retail Trade	1	0.38963 8	0.076328	1.465966	1.389638	1.465966
3018	Hotels and restaurants	1	0.51899	0.07527	1.594259	1.51899	1.594259
3019	Transport	1	0.32034 5	0.078807	1.399152	1.320345	1.399152
3020	Post and telecommunications	1	0.13764 9	0.05423	1.191879	1.137649	1.191879
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	1	0.03861 5	0.029505	1.068119	1.038615	1.068119
3022	Public Administration	1	0.25606 1	0.180207	1.436268	1.256061	1.436268
3023	Education, Health, and other services	1	0.10839 5	0.111374	1.219769	1.108395	1.219769
3024	Private Households	1	0.24682 8	0.340242	1.587071	1.246828	1.587071
3025	Others	1	0.21109 2	0.023672	1.234764	1.211092	1.234764

Source: (Implan 11 software and Database for Nigeria, 2022)

Type I Multiplier: are representative of indirect effects. This type looks only at business-to-business purchases and does not include the effects of local household spending. This Multiplier is calculated as (Direct + Indirect Effects) / Direct Effect.

Type SAM Multiplier: (where SAM stands for Social Accounting Matrix) is calculated by dividing the sum of the Direct Effects, Indirect Effects, and Induced Effects by the Direct Effects.

Table 9: Industry Coefficient of the Top 25 Sectors of the Economy in Nigeria

Code	Description	Coefficient	Supply Demand Ratio / Regional Purchase Coefficient
3001	Agriculture	0.681365	0.986766
3002	Fishing	0.000041	0.915352
3003	Mining and Quarrying	0.000017	0.439715
3004	Food and beverages	0.005098	0.912110
3005	Textiles and wearing apparel	0.000125	0.847660
3006	Wood and paper	0.002760	0.815114
3007	Petroleum, Chemical, and Non-metal mfg.	0.011805	0.722378
3008	Metal products	0.000830	0.716336
3009	Electrical and machinery	0.001108	0.706237
3010	Transport equipment	0.000126	0.708568
3011	Other manufacturing	0.000133	0.817998
3012	Recycling	0.000001	0.970897
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0.001624	0.921965
3014	Construction	0.000638	0.892407
3015	Maintenance and repair	0.000075	0.944549
3016	Wholesale Trade	0.006856	0.929491
3017	Retail Trade	0.000280	0.979336
3018	Hotels and restaurants	0.000035	0.939642
3019	Transport	0.003237	0.833201
3020	Post and telecommunications	0.000444	0.951517
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0.031361	0.978760
3022	Public Administration	0.000014	0.874961
3023	Education, Health, and other services	0.000308	0.952892
3024	Private Households	0.000000	0.847560
3025	Others	0.000349	0.964008
Total Absorption Value		0.748629	
Value Added Coefficient		0.251371	
Total Production Function		1	

Source: (Implan 11 software and Database for Nigeria, 2022)

Table 10 : Showing 2015 Expenditure Economic Impact

Impact Type	Employment	Labor Income ₦	Value Added ₦	Output ₦
Direct Effect	0.1	80,592	707,859	791,350
Indirect Effect	0	2,958	76,565	85,778
Induced Effect	0	3,940	70,968	88,136
Total Effect	0.2	87,491	855,391	965,264

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 11: Showing 2015 Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Employment	Labor Income ₦	Value Added ₦	Output ₦
3023	Education, Health, and other services	0.1	81,652	717,164	801,753
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0	2,352	86,298	89,555
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0	178	3,379	4,071
301	Agriculture	0	26	1,899	7,556
3016	Wholesale Trade	0	566	6,942	8,424
3017	Retail Trade	0	435	4,747	7,569
3020	Post and telecommunications	0	388	7,159	8,282
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0	280	6,746	8,052
309	Electrical and machinery	0	249	3,186	4,086
306	Wood and paper	0	186	2,944	3,455

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 12: 2016 Economic Impact

Impact Type	Showing 2016 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2016 Donation Impact			
	Employment	Labor Income ₦	Value Added ₦	Output ₦	Employment	Labor Income ₦	Value Added ₦	Output ₦
Direct Effect	0.2	206,667	1,815,199	2,029,300	0	25,460	223,624	250,000
Indirect Effect	0.1	7,586	196,339	219,966	0	935	24,188	27,099
Induced Effect	0.1	10,104	181,986	226,011	0	1,245	22,420	27,843
Total Effect	0.4	224,357	2,193,524	2,475,277	0.1	27,640	270,232	304,942

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 13: Showing 2016 Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Showing 2016 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2016 Donation Impact			
		Employment	Labor Income ₦	Value Added ₦	Output ₦	Employment	Labor Income ₦	Value Added ₦	Output ₦
3023	Education, Health, and other services	0.2	209,384	1,839,061	2,055,977	0	25,795	226,564	253,286
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0.1	6,031	221,297	229,651	0	743	27,263	28,292
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0	457	8,664	10,440	0	56	1,067	1,286
301	Agriculture	0	67	4,871	19,377	0	8	600	2,387
3016	Wholesale Trade	0	1,451	17,803	21,603	0	179	2,193	2,661
3017	Retail Trade	0	1,117	12,172	19,410	0	138	1,500	2,391
3020	Post and telecommunications	0	994	18,359	21,237	0	122	2,262	2,616
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0	718	17,299	20,648	0	88	2,131	2,544
309	Electrical and machinery	0	639	8,171	10,477	0	79	1,007	1,291
306	Wood and paper	0	476	7,549	8,860	0	59	930	1,091

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 14: 2017 Economic Impact

Impact Type	Showing 2017 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2017 Donation Impact			
	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
Direct Effect	0.3	247,536	2,174,162	2,430,603	0.1	66,197	581,422	650,000
Indirect Effect	0.1	9,086	235,166	263,465	0	2,430	62,889	70,457
Induced Effect	0.1	12,102	217,975	270,705	0	3,236	58,292	72,393
Total Effect	0.5	268,725	2,627,303	2,964,774	0.1	71,863	702,602	792,850

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 15: Showing 2017 Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Showing 2017 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2017 Donation Impact			
		Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
3023	Education, Health, and other services	0.3	250,790	2,202,744	2,462,556	0.1	67,067	589,065	658,545
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0.1	7,224	265,060	275,065	0	1,932	70,883	73,559
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0	547	10,378	12,505	0	146	2,775	3,344
301	Agriculture	0	80	5,834	23,209	0	21	1,560	6,207
3016	Wholesale Trade	0	1,738	21,323	25,875	0	465	5,702	6,920
3017	Retail Trade	0	1,338	14,579	23,248	0	358	3,899	6,217
3020	Post and telecommunications	0	1,191	21,990	25,437	0	318	5,881	6,803
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0	860	20,719	24,731	0	230	5,541	6,614
309	Electrical and machinery	0	766	9,787	12,549	0	205	2,617	3,356
306	Wood and paper	0	570	9,042	10,612	0	152	2,418	2,838

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 16: 2018 Economic Impact

Impact Type	Showing 2018 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2018 Donation Impact			
	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
Direct Effect	0.5	449,154	3,945,016	4,410,327	0.1	93,083	817,568	914,000
Indirect Effect	0.2	16,487	426,708	478,058	0	3,417	88,431	99,073
Induced Effect	0.2	21,959	395,515	491,194	0	4,551	81,967	101,796
Total Effect	1	487,601	4,767,239	5,379,579	0.2	101,051	987,967	1,114,869

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 17: Showing 2018 Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Showing 2018 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2018 Donation Impact			
		Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
3023	Education, Health, and other services	0.5	455,059	3,996,877	4,468,305	0.1	94,307	828,316	926,015
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0.1	13,107	480,951	499,105	0	2,716	99,673	103,435
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0.1	993	18,830	22,690	0	206	3,902	4,702
301	Agriculture	0.1	145	10,586	42,112	0	30	2,194	8,727
3016	Wholesale Trade	0	3,153	38,691	46,951	0	654	8,018	9,730
3017	Retail Trade	0	2,427	26,454	42,184	0	503	5,482	8,742
3020	Post and telecommunications	0	2,160	39,900	46,156	0	448	8,269	9,565
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0	1,560	37,595	44,875	0	323	7,791	9,300
309	Electrical and machinery	0	1,390	17,758	22,770	0	288	3,680	4,719
306	Wood and paper	0	1,035	16,406	19,255	0	214	3,400	3,990

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 18: 2019 Economic Impact

Impact Type	Showing 2019 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2019 Donation Impact			
	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
Direct Effect	0.4	297,696	2,614,727	2,923,132	0.1	122,210	1,073,394	1,200,000
Indirect Effect	0.1	10,928	282,819	316,853	0.1	4,486	116,103	130,074
Induced Effect	0.2	14,555	262,144	325,560	0.1	5,975	107,615	133,648
Total Effect	0.6	323,179	3,159,691	3,565,545	0.3	132,671	1,297,112	1,463,723

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 19 : Showing 2019 Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Showing 2019 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2019 Donation Impact			
		Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
3023	Education, Health, and other services	0.4	301,610	2,649,100	2,961,560	0.1	123,816	1,087,505	1,215,775
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0.1	8,687	318,771	330,803	0	3,566	130,861	135,801
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0.1	658	12,481	15,039	0	270	5,123	6,174
301	Agriculture	0.1	96	7,016	27,912	0	39	2,880	11,458
3016	Wholesale Trade	0	2,090	25,644	31,119	0	858	10,527	12,775
3017	Retail Trade	0	1,609	17,534	27,959	0	660	7,198	11,478
3020	Post and telecommunications	0	1,432	26,445	30,592	0	588	10,856	12,558
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0	1,034	24,918	29,743	0	425	10,229	12,210
309	Electrical and machinery	0	921	11,770	15,092	0	378	4,832	6,195
306	Wood and paper	0	686	10,874	12,762	0	2281	4,464	5,239

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 20: 2020 Economic Impact

Impact Type	Showing 2020 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2020 Donation Impact			
	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
Direct Effect	0.1	117,121	1,028,693	1,150,027	1.1	916,574	8,050,455	9,000,000
Indirect Effect	0.1	4,299	111,268	124,657	0.4	33,645	870,769	975,556
Induced Effect	0.1	5,726	103,134	128,083	0.5	44,812	807,114	1,002,364
Total Effect	0.3	127,146	1,243,095	1,402,767	2	995,031	9,728,338	10,977,919

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 21: Showing 2020 Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Showing 2020 Expenditure Impact				Showing 2020 Donation Impact			
		Employment	Labor Income ₱	Value Added ₱	Output ₱	Employment	Labor Income ₱	Value Added ₱	Output ₱
3023	Education, Health, and other services	0.1	118,660	1,042,217	1,165,145	1.1	928,623	8,156,287	9,118,314
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0	3,418	125,412	130,146	0.2	26,747	981,459	1,018,506
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0	259	4,910	5,917	0.2	2,027	38,426	46,304
301	Agriculture	0	38	2,760	10,981	0.2	295	21,602	85,937
3016	Wholesale Trade	0	822	10,089	12,243	0.1	6,435	78,955	95,810
3017	Retail Trade	0	633	6,898	11,000	0.1	4,953	53,985	86,084
3020	Post and telecommunications	0	563	10,404	12,036	0	4,409	81,422	94,189
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0	407	9,803	11,702	0	3,184	76,719	91,575
309	Electrical and machinery	0	362	4,631	5,937	0	2,836	36,238	46,465
306	Wood and paper	0	270	4,278	5,021	0	2,111	33,479	39,292

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 22: Showing 2021 Expenditure Economic Impact

Impact Type	Employment	Labor Income ₱	Value Added ₱	Output ₱
Direct Effect	1.8	1,527,623	13,417,425	15,000,000
Indirect Effect	0.7	56,076	1,451,281	1,625,926
Induced Effect	0.8	74,686	1,345,189	1,670,606
Total Effect	3.3	1,658,385	16,213,896	18,296,532

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 23: Showing 2021 Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
3023	Education, Health, and other services	1.8	1,547,705	13,593,811	15,197,190
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	0.4	44,579	1,635,766	1,697,510
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0.3	3,378	64,044	77,173
301	Agriculture	0.3	492	36,003	143,228
3016	Wholesale Trade	0.2	10,725	131,591	159,684
3017	Retail Trade	0.1	8,254	89,974	143,473
3020	Post and telecommunications	0	7,348	135,704	156,981
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0	5,307	127,866	152,625
309	Electrical and machinery	0	4,727	60,396	77,442
306	Wood and paper	0	3,518	55,798	65,487

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 24: Showing Anticipated Future Expenditure Economic Impact

Impact Type	Nayomee Project				Woodbury & Evergreen Projects (Values X 2)				Transactions			
	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
Direct Effect	12.6	9,150,429	70,138,034	100,999,999	6.2	4,529,915	34,721,799	50,000,000	28.8	717,008	38,720,827	49,000,000
Indirect Effect	13.3	1,238,822	26,269,585	30,608,987	6.6	613,278	13,004,745	15,152,964	3.3	382,567	9,387,742	10,343,528
Induced Effect	5.4	489,951	8,824,603	10,959,374	2.7	242,550	4,368,615	5,425,433	0.6	51,855	933,976	1,159,916
Total Effect	31.3	10,879,202	105,232,221	142,568,360	15.5	5,385,744	52,095,159	70,578,396	32.7	1,151,431	49,042,545	60,503,444

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 25: Showing Anticipated Top 10 Gainers from the Foundation's Project Activities by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Showing Nayomee Project Expenditure Impact				Showing Woodbury & Evergreen Project Expenditure Impact			
		Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺	Employment	Labor Income ₺	Value Added ₺	Output ₺
3014	Construction	12.6	9,159,496	70,207,533	101,100,079	6.2	4,534,404	34,756,204	50,049,544
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	4.2	478,427	17,555,196	18,217,846	2.1	236,845	8,690,691	9,018,736
301	Agriculture	3.5	6,245	457,099	1,818,420	1.8	3,091	226,286	900,208
3016	Wholesale Trade	2.8	193,213	2,370,600	2,876,691	1.4	95,650	1,173,564	1,424,104
308	Metal products	1.6	212,609	2,483,884	3,033,123	0.8	105,252	1,229,645	1,501,546
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	1.6	19,236	364,683	439,444	0.8	9,523	180,536	217,547

309	Electrical and machinery	1.1	141,515	1,808,261	2,318,609	0.5	70,057	895,179	1,147,826
3017	Retail Trade	1	75,550	823,525	1,313,190	0.5	37,401	407,686	650,094
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0.9	124,372	2,996,725	3,577,006	0.4	61,570	1,483,527	1,770,795
306	Wood and paper	0.7	92,981	1,474,563	1,730,602	0.3	46,030	729,981	856,734

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)

Table 26: Showing the Top 10 Foundation's Transactional Activities Impact by sectors of the economy

Sector	Description	Employment	Labor Income	Value Added	Output
		t	₱	₱	₱
3025	Others	28.8	717,139	38,727,896	49,008,946
3021	Financial intermediation and business services	1.6	181,704	6,667,364	6,919,034
3013	Electricity, gas, and water	0.5	5,715	108,342	130,552
301	Agriculture	0.3	583	42,640	169,629
306	Wood and paper	0.3	40,289	638,931	749,873
3020	Post and telecommunications	0.3	57,371	1,059,556	1,225,683
3016	Wholesale Trade	0.3	17,649	216,542	262,771
308	Metal products	0.2	28,178	329,200	401,993
309	Electrical and machinery	0.1	15,608	199,435	255,722
307	Petroleum, Chemical and Non-metal mfg.	0.1	16,687	402,070	479,926

Source: (Author's Calculation, 2022)